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Results of Long-Term Forecasting and Strategic Analysis of Effective Organization of Modern Housing Stock Management

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***Abstract:** This article highlights the results of a long-term forecast and strategic analysis of effective management of modern housing stock, and also presents a classification of types of housing stock. The main components of the housing problem in the Republic of Uzbekistan, problematic situations of the housing stock, which are complex in nature, are identified.*

In conclusion, the main tasks of effective management of modern housing stock are defined and proposals for its improvement are developed.

***Key words:** strategy, housing stock, management, construction, population, technology, forecasts.*

Introduction

The strategic approach is increasingly used in the modern public administration system. Currently, the importance of strategic planning is increasing both at the state level and at the level of individual industries and enterprises. Such an important sector of life support as housing and communal services is no exception. This network is one of the main parts of the regional infrastructure and, with proper management and development by the state, can function at a high level. Providing the population with housing is one of the priority areas of the socio-economic policy of the state and is the direction of

improving the quality of their life, socio-economic development of the regions and the country. The development of a concept of long-term state policy based on the principles of strategic analysis, planning and forecasting in the field of effective organization of housing management in the state program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Active Investments and Social Development" and emphasized in the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. In particular:

For the effective organization of management of the modern housing stock, a gradual transition to modern management of the industry is considered necessary. To do this, introduce criteria and methods for assessing the performance of housing management personnel and key performance indicators (KPI); it is necessary to create a modern remuneration system. At the same time, the monthly salary is determined based on the work done by the civil servant, its efficiency, quality, complexity, correctness of the work in practice and other criteria; In exchange for the creation of a modern remuneration system, it is necessary to reduce the number of civil servants, take measures for social protection and retraining, that is:

1. Dissemination of modern management methods. This includes a list of tasks and functions of government agencies that will be transferred to the private sector through the use of outsourcing, crowdsourcing and public-private partnerships; it is envisaged to revise the number of administrative staff and reduce inefficient government units through the use of outsourcing, crowdsourcing and public-private partnerships.
2. Gradual transition to advanced management and the principles of "smart" management in modern management. In this:

implementation of a system for training and retraining professional managers in government agencies taking into account advanced foreign experience;

specialization of the activities of government agencies in direct work with citizens;

creation of management entities as "helpers of the people, business partners of entrepreneurs";

training in advanced tools (methods) of strategic management and risk management in public and economic management;

provision is made for the creation of a system for continuous assessment of the performance of the manager.

3. Implementation of a system for training employees in short-term and medium-term advanced training courses.
4. Development of a concept for long-term public policy based on the principles of strategic analysis, planning and forecasting in the effective management of the industry. Strategic planning mechanisms for this; provision is made for the creation of structures for strategic analysis and forecasting in the ministries and departments of the designated states.
5. Improving the financial basis for the activities of citizens' self-government bodies. This involves the introduction of effective mechanisms for attracting funds from citizens and organizations on a voluntary basis by civil assemblies.
6. Consistent continuation of the affordable housing construction program, improvement of standard house designs, use of energy-efficient technologies, adoption of measures to use modern and inexpensive building materials.

This includes: internal and external structures of houses, replacement of building materials with acceptable, inexpensive and high-quality building materials, optimization of the cost of building materials by supporting manufacturers; Price optimization by revising the agricultural road when placing a 2-story, 2- and 3-room house in the general plan; construction of 15,010 units of affordable housing in rural areas and for special categories of citizens; construction of 355 multi-story buildings in cities is planned.

1. Develop a renovation program based on foreign experience after a full inventory of multi-story housing stock. In this case, the multi-story housing stock will be completely decommissioned. To this end, it is envisaged to approve renovation programs for the phased construction of new housing on the site of obsolete multi-story buildings in order to prevent emergencies and ensure the safety of citizens living in apartment buildings.

Thanks to renovation and housing construction programs, more than 19 million square meters of modern housing will be built in cities instead of old houses, and more than 275 thousand families will be able to move to new areas. Inspection of 1,854 old houses built before 1991 and completion of construction and reconstruction work on 268 houses undergoing reconstruction based on the results of instrumental studies. Separately, it is necessary to study the historical and cultural significance of the houses.

2. Improvement of heating systems of the republican housing stock. On the territory of the republic, 5 local boiler houses will be reconstructed and 1.7 km of heat supply networks will be repaired. Support professional management companies to reduce administrative costs in HOAs. In order to reduce administrative costs of HOAs, the project provides for their transfer to investors on the basis of public-private partnership. Therefore, it is necessary to solve organizational, economic, legal and technical problems of housing and communal services management, which determines the development strategy of this industry as one of the main areas of public administration. From this point of view, the implementation and improvement of strategic development tools in the housing and communal services sector requires comprehensive research.

Literature review

The study is devoted to the results of long-term forecasting and strategic analysis of effective management of modern housing stock, as well as scientific research conducted by domestic and foreign scientists. In particular, scientific research by O. Yu. Shevchenko shows that the rating is defined as the distance separating a certain enterprise from the established standard, and that it is of great importance in assessing the effectiveness of the mechanism of financial management of housing stock, as well as the possibility of forecasting their activities by assessing them [4], as well as scientific research related to the description of financial management of the housing stock and management companies with an emphasis on their efficiency systems through a rating assessment system, as well as the formation of conclusions related to the identification, control and reduction of risks that may arise in the future are reflected in scientific research and published works of foreign scientists, such as J.K. Mohammed, A.O. Suleiman [5], H. He, H.-J. Tsai, S. Hamori [6], Hal Pawson, Julie Lawson, Vivienne Milligan [7], Xing Quan Zhang, Sopon Pornchokchai [8] and Irina Gensler [9].

According to T. L. Kappusheva, "Having a developed and implemented strategy is the most important element of successful development of any industry. In order for regions to be able to function and develop sustainably, they are forced to move to strategic management, and their main tools are: development scenario, development concept, economic forecasting, targeted comprehensive programs and a mechanism for implementing the goals of regional strategic management." [10]

Research methodology

Economic analysis, statistical grouping, systematic and comparative analysis and other methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results

The importance of focusing on the reproduction of the housing stock and its impact on providing the population with housing is associated not only with the difficult situation in the housing sector, but also with the consistent implementation of programs for the country's socio-economic development, which is determined by the quality of life of various segments of society. However, the impact of unresolved structural constraints of a number of social and institutional problems has caused internal problems in the production of modern housing. Among them, the most important are: imbalance of supply and demand in the housing market; lack of an effective mechanism for mutual cooperation between government bodies and administration, entrepreneurs, contractors, and representatives of the population; that private investors are not sufficiently encouraged to build housing and their subsequent activities; untimely completion of current and major repairs of the housing stock; ineffective operation of the mortgage lending system. To date, no scientific research has been conducted by scientists on the system of reproduction of the modern housing stock, the factors of its formation, functioning, and development based on market conditions. All of the above problems indicate a systemic crisis in the housing sector. As a result, this leads to increased risks when using modern housing stock and its repair.

To build a modern housing stock and effectively manage it in the future, it is necessary to implement the following:

- formation of new effective organizational and economic models to prevent disproportions of regulatory and legal information and rules;
- consideration of ways to use effective management tools to ensure high-quality and affordable real estate;
- indicators of its assessment in the market are important for preventing and eliminating structural and communication problems of the housing stock;
- implementation of a cluster approach to the formation and development of the housing stock reproduction market by providing the population with the opportunity to use innovative mortgage lending tools and strengthening the role of local governments.

Many developed countries, especially the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are also trying to positively solve problems associated with the development of the housing stock real estate market. Based on the researcher's analysis, the practical application of such problems and their solutions mentioned above allows us to extrapolate positive results.

Thus, the effective development of reproduction and management of the modern housing stock, taking into account the factors that ensure the stability of supply and demand in the housing market - the development of tools for identifying, assessing and regulating risks, improving the quality of housing construction. investment projects, as well as ensuring mutually beneficial cooperation. At the same time, the essence of the study shows that the essence of theoretical knowledge about the reproduction of the modern housing stock and its management as a science in the field of housing is not based on sufficient terminological concepts in the research works of research workers. based scientists.

As a result of generalizing and systematizing the opinions of various economists, the following conclusions were made:

1. Reproduction and management of the modern housing stock includes production, distribution, exchange and consumption.
2. The existence and redistribution of invested surplus value is a prerequisite for the production of new innovative types of advanced services and its increase.
3. The process of reproduction and effective management of the modern housing stock includes various types of economic activity associated with certain risks, aimed at obtaining and redistributing income.
4. In the process of reproduction and effective management of the modern housing stock, new construction, major repairs, reconstruction, modernization and technical re-equipment will be carried out in order to increase its durability by restoring its structural and communication condition. In accordance with the territorial location of our republic, a comprehensive methodological approach is proposed for assessing the trends in the development of the housing market. Thanks to their constant cyclical monitoring, their implementation allows us to predict possible problems in the development of the housing stock, the real estate market.

It can be said that from the point of view of the theory of hedonic demand, the price of a residential building reflects the sum of the characteristics of the conditions, amenities and utilities existing in it. In this regard, the economic literature has identified problems with servicing the following consumer characteristics of residential buildings:

- a) fundamentality;
- b) individuality, uniqueness, diversity (heterogeneity);
- c) comfort for living;
- d) the period of construction of housing;
- e) the ability of the property owner to control the rate of physical depreciation;
- f) discrepancy between product characteristics (asymmetry of ideas about the product) - real estate objects from the point of view of the manufacturer and the consumer. From the point of view of the consumer, in most cases, an apartment, a residential building or part of it is considered a product that satisfies the need for housing. According to the position of the manufacturer (construction organization), the product is a finished apartment, plot of land or a private house.
- g) this leads to such consequences as high cost of residential buildings, low purchase market, rent instead of purchase, use of residential real estate as a means of saving (investment);
- h) in exchange for an increase in the cost of housing services associated with the sale of housing, the owner agrees to an exchange of housing, that is, the unification of housing;
- i) such problems as the emergence of a new need for households to improve their housing conditions associated with an increase in the number of families, an improvement in their well-being, etc., while the need for residential buildings is practically not satisfied.
- j) affecting the aesthetic appearance of the territory on which it is located.

Having combined the above problems, the following definition of the object of reproduction and management of residential buildings is proposed: "Residential real estate is an object of constant vital

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